

USE OF INTERACTIVE GRAPHIC DEVICES IN THE ACQUISITION, PROCESSING
AND DISPLAY OF ENVIRONMENTAL SATELLITE DATA

Roland E. Nagle

Naval Environmental Prediction Research Facility
Monterey, California 93943

Abstract

The AN/FMC-2(A) -- a minicomputer-based, interactive-graphics display system that is designed to acquire, process, and display both conventional environmental data and products and environmental satellite data -- is described. The system, a hybrid consisting of a microprocessor-based communications front-end and a minicomputer-based display device, supports acquisition and cataloging of data and products in realtime with simultaneous use of the system for display and manipulation of previously acquired products. The systems' applications functions are illustrated.

1. Introduction

The use of minicomputer-based interactive graphic display systems for processing and displaying environmental satellite imagery has become commonplace within the research community (see for example, Billingsby and Hasler; Pressman and Holyer; Schramm, Zeleny, Nagle, and Weinstein; and Smith). However, current operational systems such as the Navy Environmental Display Station (NEDS) and the Automated Field Observing System (AFOS) are designed primarily to handle alphanumeric and graphic products and, at best, have only a limited capability to display environmental satellite data (including imagery).

The system described in this paper, the AN/FMC-2(A), is a computer-based communications and satellite data processing and display system that was designed to allow the synergistic use of satellite data and conventional environmental observations and analyses. The goal is to provide a device that will allow the efficient and flexible use of satellite data in the Navy's environmental support system.

2. Hardware Configuration

A functional diagram of the AN/FMC-2(A) hardware is shown in Figure 1. The system consists of two interconnected modules, a communications front-end and an interactive graphics system, connected through a bi-directional high

speed digital bus. The communications front-end was inherited from the AN/FMC-2 (NEDS-1A) and consists of an array of single board microcomputers (SBC). Each SBC is dedicated to a single function: one controlling the Automated Weather Network (AWN) line, a second for the Naval Environmental Data Network (NEDN), a third to handle digitized GOES-TAP, TIROS-N APT, and WEFAX data, and a fourth that acts as a master controller for the microcomputer system. Vacant slots are available in the communications front-end chassis for future expansion.

The interactive graphics system is based on a Data General Eclipse S-140 minicomputer, a state-of-the-art, 16-bit computer. The S-140 is equipped with 256K Bytes of memory, a hardware floating point processor, and two 147 M Byte Winchester disk drives. Each disk is interfaced to the S-140 through separate controllers which greatly reduces conflicts when accessing data.

Control of the system is provided through a "smart terminal". This is a microcomputer based alphanumeric display terminal. It is the only method of operating the system and allows several levels of security. Two access levels are allowed. The first is for a limited number of personnel who are allowed access to the realtime disk operating system's (RDOS) command language instructions (CLI). CLI commands allows an operator access to files up to his defined level of security and to the full RDOS functions. The second access level is for system operators. At this level, the user is only allowed to exercise application modules through the SPADS Executive. Thus, some level of control is provided as to who has access to system functions.

A second level of control is provided for classified files. A users access and security level master file is maintained in a secure file on the system. Upon starting up the system, this file is transferred transparently from the S-140 to the smart terminal. A user must logon the system using ID and password. The smart terminal checks the user's ID against his access and security level. Users without "system" access are precluded from executing CLI's on the system and/or from accessing files above their defined security levels.

Functional Diagram of the AN/FMC-2(A) Hardware
Figure 1

Graphics capabilities are provided through a Programmable Graphics Processor (PGP). This device drives a long-persistent phosphor color monitor and allows full SPADS graphics and image display manipulation capabilities. The PGP contains sixteen (16) 512x512x1 bit planes of solid state refresh memory, a zoom and scroll, and a memory multiplexor board. The PGP supports a graph tablet/ pen system for full man-machine interactive capabilities. Eight planes of the solid state refresh provide the primary output to the color monitor. All eight planes may be used for displaying an image in 256 colors or greyscale. An image may also be displayed in 64 greyscale with two color overlays, red and green. The remaining eight planes of solid state refresh memory may be used for storage of an additional image or binary graphics products. These data can be displayed under program control through the use of the memory multiplexor board. This board allows any combination of eight of the sixteen planes to be displayed on the color monitor.

Printer output is provided through a Versatec V-80 electrostatic printer/plotter. Alphanumerics and graphics can be outputted to this device to produce hardcopy. The V-80 can also be used to produce greyscale copies of satellite images of relatively low quality.

3. Operating System

The operating system employed on the AN/FMC-2(A) is Data General's Realtime Disk Operating System (RDOS). RDOS is a sophisticated, mature operating system that supports the execution of two programs simultaneously, one in a foreground partition and a second in a background partition. The foreground partition is assigned the highest priority on access to the CPU; therefore, the program that manages the acquisition of data transmitted from the communications front-end resides, transparently, in the foreground partition. The SATDAT Processing and Display System (SPADS) Executive resides in the background partition and allows execution of all SPADS functions simultaneously with the acquisition of data being performed in the foreground.

4. Utilities and Applications

A functioning model of an AN/FMC-2(A) is on display at this conference and the capabilities of the system can be viewed. Therefore, only the unique capabilities of the AN/FMC-2(A) will be described in this paper, without illustration, primarily to limit the length of the paper. Other functions are indicated by title only.

Communications Subsystem

The communications front-end can simultaneously accept message and graphic traffic available over both the NEDN and AWN. Priority message headers are passed to the Smart Terminal and are displayed on the A/N CRT in a topline banner. Messages, including ARQ's, generated on the AN/FMC-2(A) can also be transmitted over either of these communication lines. Analog GOES-TAP data are digitized and routed to the S-140 in realtime and concurrently with the acquisition of data over both the AWN and NEDN lines. Data available over the AWN include surface and upper air observations, forecasts, severe weather and high seas warnings, radar summaries, FNOG variable exception vector (VEV) graphics, etc. All message and graphic products transmitted over the NEDN can be received by the AN/FMC-2(A). In addition, NEPRF has successfully received FNOG fields in binary grid-point format transmitted over the NEDN. Thus, the capability to distribute any FNOG field to AN/FMC-2(A) sites in grid-point versus VEV format over the NEDN has been demonstrated.

Hardware Checks

This option executes diagnostics on the display subsystem hardware. An Auto-test mode of nine (9) user selectable options is available. This allows the user to select the time interval for tests (0.1-5.0 seconds). A summary of hardware diagnostics can be output to printer.

Catalog Functions

Allows display and updating of catalogs of file names contained on the system. Allows renaming, deletion, purging, or entering new files into the catalogs. Allows the generation of GOES-TAP images and Mercator transformations from raw GOES-TAP image files, the calibration of these data, and the entry of the new GOES-TAP or Mercator image into the appropriate catalog. The user may select three (3) resolutions when creating a GOES-TAP image. Each image is a 512X512X8 bit array and an image may be created at 1X, 2X, or 4X resolution. The 1X option produces a subset of the original sector at full resolution. The 2X option produces an image at one-half the original resolution and the 4X option produces the full sector at one-fourth the original resolution. Selection of any resolution produces a corresponding calibration table for use of the image in a quantitative manner. The image is constructed in the solid state refresh memory and appears on the color monitor as the image is being created. Upon completion, the image is read back from the solid state refresh memory and a disk file of the image is created. The image file name is then entered into the catalog of untransformed GOES images.

The Create Mercator Image option is very similar to the above process except the raw GOES-TAP data are transformed into mercator projection.

There are, currently, twenty-one (21) catalogs in the AN/FMC-2(A) system, of which twenty are active. Message and graphics catalogs for data received over either AWN or the NEDN can contain up to 438 entries; with one exception, all other catalogs can have up to 219 entries.

Nineteen entries within any catalog can be displayed on the alphanumeric CRT at one time. The display can be advanced one page at a time (19 entries), or one page backward at a time. Each catalog can be advanced so that the last (most current) data in the catalog can be displayed.

The catalog for FNOG grid-point fields contains a sub-catalog for the following products:

- Northern Hemisphere Polar Stereographic
- Southern Hemisphere Polar Stereographic
- Mercator
- Ocean Thermal Structure
- NORAPS Polar Stereographic

When any sub-catalog option is selected, the system will display a list of all products within the selected catalog that are resident on the disk system.

Display Functions

Create Field Contour Overlay

This option allows the generation/display of contour fields. Contours can be generated from either FNOG grid-point fields or VEV graphics. If the contours are to be generated from grid-point fields, the display capabilities are very general; contours can be generated for twenty-one standard areas which include FNOG Ocean Thermal Structures (OTS) areas. Random user-defined sub-areas can be selected to produce contours at 1:60, 1:30, 1:15, or 1:7.5 million map scale in Polar Stereographic projection. For Mercator projection products, a comparable capability exists with either standard or user selected display areas. Map scales allow display of products covering longitudinal bands of 120, 60, 30, and 15 degrees; latitudinal coverage is scaled to these bands in order to retain the proper map projection. Products can be recontoured with user-selected origin and contour intervals. Grid-point data in Polar Stereographic projection can be transformed into Mercator projection.

VEV graphics received over either the AWN or the NEDN can be displayed. Contours can be generated using default parameters or user-selected parameters. The default option extracts display parameters from an internal table. The VEV graphics is displayed in the green overlay

plane and the corresponding geographic background is brought up automatically in the red plane. With user selected options, the product(s) can be zoomed, offset, rotated, displayed in different colors, and presented as solid, long-dashed, or short-dashed contours. Multiple products can be displayed (with geography) with either option.

Display Geographical Overlay

Create Contour Overlay File

There are two sub-options under this function: the first allows the creation of a disk file in raster format (512X512X1 bit) of any graphic which has been displayed or generated on either of the two overlay planes. The purpose of this function is to provide very quick display of previously generated products. For example, a chart in Mercator projection for the North Atlantic operational area consisting of the surface pressure contours, marine boundary layer winds, frontal positions, and significant weather symbols can be generated on the AN/FMC-2(A)'s display. This product can then be written to disk. The product can be recalled for display in about one second. The contour overlay function is particularly useful in the generation of those products which require the application of the AN/FMC-2(A)'s man-machine interactive capabilities. The second option performs a similar function but operates with both the overlay files and an image. The two graphics contained in the overlay planes are merged into the corresponding image being displayed. The resulting image is written to a disk file and is entered into the "Image/Overlay" catalog; the file is named in accordance with the catalog number of the field contained in the overlay plane.

Display Overlay File

Perform Field Operation

This option can only be executed if FNOC grid-point fields are available on the system. Three sub-options are available under this selection: Scale Separation, Frontal Analysis (GGθ), and Wind Derivatives. The contour field generated by these options can be displayed in any one of the twenty-one standard areas, in a user-defined area, or over the area of a previously displayed image. Recontouring of the product is allowed if desired.

By selecting the scale separation option, the scale separation technique can be applied to any FNOC polar stereographic field. Standard smoothing options can be selected or the user can specify his own amount-of-smoothing. The resulting fields (SD, SR, SL or SV) are written to disk and entered into the catalog. The fields may be contoured and displayed using the Create Field Contour Overlay option.

Selection of option 2 in the sub-menu permits the application of the GGθ algorithm (frontal analysis) to a FNOC grid-point field. This option is restricted to fields in polar stereographic projection.

When the Wind Derivatives option is selected, partial derivatives of the selected field are computed, i.e., $\partial/\partial x$, $\partial/\partial y$. This option allows the combination of the partial derivatives of the field to produce divergence, relative vorticity, shearing deformation, stretching deformation, vorticity advection, and temperature advection. The selected parameter can be displayed and recontoured.

Display Image

Enhance Image

Zoom

Load Enhancement File

Create Cross-Section Contour

This option requires several prerequisites to allow execution. First, a full set of FNOC's polar stereographic analysis/forecast fields must be resident on the system; these include height, temperature, wind and humidity fields. Second, a contour field from the current analysis fields must be present on the color monitor. An image may also be resident, but this is not essential. When the cross-section option is selected, all of the FNOC fields corresponding to the date and time of the field being displayed are loaded into the extended memory of the S-140; this process takes about one minute. The beginning and end points of the cross-section are then defined through use of either the graph pen or keyboard entry. When this process is complete, a new menu is displayed on the A/N CRT from which the pressure limits of the desired cross-section can be selected. Next, a menu of those parameters which can be incorporated in the cross-section are displayed; these include temperature, geostrophic wind shear, potential temperature, geopotential height, geostrophic wind, analyzed wind, mixing ratio, and dew point. If an infrared image had previously been displayed, the system can display the cloud top location along the cross-section with either a vertical line or a "+". The color of the cross-section coordinate graph is then selected from eight available colors and, the character of the contour to be displayed is selected and the character (solid, long dash, or short dash) of the cross-section contour can be specified. Contour origin and interval is selected and then the field is displayed on the color monitor. Additional parameters can be selected and included in the cross-section display in any of the eight colors provided.

Color Slice

Create Threshold Overlay file

Turn Planes On/Off

This option is very straightforward. Under keyboard control, the user can turn on or off either overlay plane or both overlay planes. An image can be turned on or off, or the image and both overlay planes can be turned on or off.

Run Cursor

Selection of this option activates the graph tablet and pen. Using the graph pen, data being displayed on the color monitor can be zoomed by factors of 2X, 4X, and 8X and simultaneously scrolled in accordance with the movement of the pen. The zoom capability is performed in hardware by pixel replication. The graph pen can also be used to turn off or on the video gates (overlay planes) or the image. An additional capability under this option allows the use of the graph pen to freehand erase or draw on either overlay plane (red or green).

Print Hardcopy

This option allows a hardcopy of the information being displayed on the color monitor to be output to the V-80 printer/plotter. The first sub-option is for making a hardcopy of just the overlay planes; a hardcopy of multiple color displays, such as a cross-section, can also be produced with this option. The system allows the user to type in a label for the product, if desired. Up to 99 copies can be produced automatically. The first copy takes about 40 seconds.

Greyscale images (low quality) with merged overlays can also be produced. It is recommended that an image be enhanced (option 7) over a range of 0-45 prior to producing a hardcopy. A hardcopy of an image can be produced in about one minute.

Extract Information From an Image

This option contains many sub-options that allow flexible applications of the interactive capabilities of the AN/FMC-2(A).

Generate a Horizontal Weather Depiction Chart

Selection of this option provides entrance to a set of routines that allow a horizontal weather depiction chart (HWD) to be generated. The majority of functions under this option are executed through the use of the graph pen. Frontal positions can be indicated by selection of appropriate symbols from the template provided on the graph tablet. A nephanalysis can be produced by outlining major cloud areas with scalloped boundaries. The type of cloud can be

specified and the full set of WBAN weather symbols are available and can be entered into the HWD. The entire product when completed can be stored as a disk file and entered into the SPADS catalog.

Display Parameters

Selection of this option creates a display of the SPADS Executive state parameters. The system log is displayed containing information on the last image that was displayed, the enhancement, contour field, and other parameters related to the PGP solid state refresh display.

5. Summary

The AN/FMC-2(A) is a powerful system that allows the acquisition and processing of both conventional and environmental satellite data at moderate cost. The system has significant growth potential and could be upgraded to acquire digital satellite data. For example, an S-140 minicomputer is used as the front-end processor on another NEPRF system to ingest the full stretched mode (1.747 Mb/sec) GOES readout data. The major limitation of such systems related to disk transfer latency have been largely overcome by providing separate controllers to the systems disk drives and running the communications and applications modules in separate partitions within the computer. The Navy has seventeen (17) AN/FMC-2(A)'s on order and the first units have been installed at NEPRF and FNOG in Monterey, Calif. Other units are scheduled for installation at operational locations after the system undergoes a test and evaluation period. The deployment of these devices offers new opportunities for the effective use of satellite data in the Navy's environmental support system.

6. References

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